

Storage;

A well-dried cowpea seed with 10% moisture content (seeds that make a cracking sound when crushed between the teeth) should be stored in a well aerated place.

Bruchid control

- Practice seed dressing with chemicals such Actelic powder or wood ash for seeds to be planted.
- Keep storage place clean fumigated.
- Store in dry airtight containers.
- Store the cowpea harvest un-threshed (in pods).
- Regularly display the stored grains on sunshine for at least four days for long storage.

TRIPLE-BAGGING TECHNOLOGY

A: sun dry the seed, **B:** clean the seed; **C:** Fold the top of bag 1; **D:** Insert bag 2 fold; **E:** insert bag 3 fold; **F:** Pour seed in bag 3, unfold the top; **G & H:** Tie bag 1, unfold bag 2 and tie; **I & J:** Unfold bag 3, twist the top and tie tightly. Tie the knot again with a rope. **K:** Safely stored seeds.

Variety	Days to maturity	Yields kg/ha	Seed colour
NAROCOW 1	73-75	1500-2200	White
NAROCOW 2	74-76	1300-2100	White
NAROCOW 3	74-76	1500-2200	White
NAROCOW 4	73-75	1500-2200	White
NAROCOW 5	75-77	1300-2100	White
NAROCOW 6	76-78	1500-2200	White
SECOW 1T	85 - 90	700-1200	Tan/brown
SECOW 2W	80 - 85	1000-1500	Bold white
SECOW 3B	72 - 74	1100-2500	Black
SECOW 4W	73 - 76	1200-2300	White
SECOW 5T	73 - 77	1500-2500	Tan/brown
ALEGI	85 - 90	500-1000	White
EBALAT	85 - 90	500-1000	White

NAROCOW 1 to 6 are the latest varieties that tolerant to drought and moderately resist common diseases. SECOW 2 to 3, were released five years and bred for resistance virus diseases. SECOW 1&2 were the first improved varieties bred for high yields and early maturity. Alegi and Ebalat are local land races commonly grown in northern and eastern, respectively

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CLUSTER GRANARY SEED PROJECT

NaSARRI

Quality Cowpea Seed Production Guide

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INTRODUCTION

Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp), is one of the major legume crops grown in the semi arid regions of Uganda. It is an important food crop for the resource poor, supporting household needs from the early seedling stages to post-harvesting time. In Uganda, the crop is an eminent source of food and household income to the resource poor and about 90% of the crop is grown in the eastern and northern districts of the country.

Step by step guide of cowpea production:-

1. Land preparation.

Always clear the land of bushes, shrubs and stubbles. Plough 2-3 times to ensure fine seed bed for planting. Create drainage channels in places that flood. You can use hand hoe, oxen or tractor for land preparation.

2. Seed preparation for planting.

Always use pest and disease free seeds. Sort out damaged and malformed seeds from seed meant for planting. If needed, treat seed before planting. Acquire seed for planting should done early before land preparation. 6 kg can plant an acre.

3. Planting.

Make sure the seed bed is fine and well drained. For better plant population and good performance of the crop, row planting is recommended. Sow seeds not more than 5cm deep for early and uniform germination. Do not planted in flooded place. Plant on on-set of rains.

4. Spacing.

Spacing between rows and within rows for optimum yield include; 60cm x 30cm, 75cm x 45cm, and 50cm x 20cm. For semi-erect, spreading and erect varieties.

5. Weed management.

Weed cowpea 2 or 3 times depending the fineness of the seed bed. First weeding is at 2-3 weeks after planting, second weeding is at 5-7 weeks and the last weeding (optional) is at 11-12 weeks after planting. Do not weed at the peak of flowering. Weed can be done using hand hoe, oxen, tractor or herbicides depending on farmers capacity and scale of production.

6. Thinning.

Thinning is done after first weeding. Thin to 1 to 2 plants per hill/hole and leave healthy plants.

7. Rouging.

Involves removal of diseased, pest infested and off types (plants that look different from others).

8. Management of common pests.

Pests are major constrain to cowpea production and affect it from seedling stage to storage. They include; soil-borne pests, leaf chewing and sucking pests, Flower chewing and sucking pests, Pod suckers and borers, and storage pests (weevils / Bruchids). Field scouting, used of clean seeds, intercropping and trapping are safe approaches. At high infestation, field sprays with recommended, insecticides is encourage at vegetative; flowering; pod forming and filling stages. Seed treatment.

9. Management of Common diseases.

Cowpea is affected by fungal, bacterial, viral and nutrient deficiency diseases. These include; scab, fusarium wilt, stem and root rot, anthracnose, leaf spot, yellow and brown rust, powdery mildew, leaf blight, etc. Management approaches include; field surveillance, rouging, use of resistant varieties, timely planting, crop rotation, intercropping, removal of volunteer crops, chemical sprays, etc.

10. Harvesting.

Cowpea matures 70 – 90 days. Harvesting is done when the pods are fully mature(have turn colour from green to yellow to “creamish” or brown for purple pods). Pods are picked by hands.

11. Drying.

Pods should not be allowed to dry in the field to avoid loss of seeds through shattering. After harvest spread the pods on clean surface preferably tarpaulins under direct sunshine for at least 3-4 days before threshing.

12. Threshing.

Cowpea is threshed when the pods are brittle, they easily shutter when pressed. Always thresh on clean surface to avoid contamination. Threshed cowpea should be dried on direct sunshine for at least 1-2days before storage.